

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

UOT 581.585.5

Memmedova Gunay Vagif qızı
Azerbaijan, Baku

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828505>

BIOECOLOGICAL AND ANATOMICAL-MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE SPECIES SENECIO GRANDIDENTATUS LEBED

Мамедова Гюнай Вагиф кызы
Азербайджан, Баку

БИОЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И АНАТОМО-МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВИДА SENECIO GRANDIDENTATUS LEBED

Summary

The main objective of this study is to investigate the systematic position of the species *Senecio grandidentatus*, a member of the *Senecio* genus in the flora of Azerbaijan, through bioecological and anatomical-morphological research. The species' systematic position was determined according to established guidelines, and the morphological characteristics of the vegetative organs were studied. Specimens prepared with the help of the MBS-2 binocular loupe were examined under modern microscopes.

The results of this study can be used for phylogenetic evaluation among the species of the *Senecio* genus, species identification, conservation efforts, and botanical education. Research has shown that the leaves of the plant *Senecio grandidentatus* have a dorsiventral structure, the leaves are amphistomatic, the mesophyll is of the heterogeneous type, the conductive bundles are of the open-collateral type, and the layered collenchyma cells in the stem give a wavy appearance to the stem when combined with chlorenchyma. Strong xylem development was observed in the root, and schizogenous secretion cavities were formed in the rhizome. Additionally, the bioecological features and some diagnostic traits of the species *S. grandidentatus* were also identified. For the first time, the species *Senecio grandidentatus* was anatomically and morphologically studied in the flora of Azerbaijan, and based on the findings, its systematic position was evaluated.

Резюме

Основной целью данного исследования является изучение систематического положения вида *Senecio grandidentatus*, представителя рода *Senecio*, во флоре Азербайджана путем биоэкологических и анатомо-морфологических исследований. Систематическое положение вида было определено в соответствии с установленными правилами, изучены морфологические характеристики вегетативных органов. Образцы, приготовленные с помощью бинокулярной лупы МБС-2, изучались в современных микроскопах.

Результаты данного исследования могут быть использованы для филогенетической оценки видов рода *Senecio*, идентификации видов, охраны природы и ботанического образования. Исследования показали, что листья растения *Senecio grandidentatus* имеют дорсивентральную структуру, листья амфистоматичны, мезофилл неоднороден, проводящие пучки имеют открыто-коллатеральный тип, а слоистые клетки колленхимы в стебле придают стеблю волнистый вид в сочетании с хлоренхимой. В корневище отмечено сильное развитие ксилемы, а в корневище сформированы шизогенные полости секреции. Кроме того, были выявлены биоэкологические особенности и некоторые диагностические признаки вида *S. grandidentatus*. Впервые во флоре Азербайджана анатомически и морфологически изучен вид *Senecio grandidentatus*, и на основании полученных данных дана оценка его систематического положения.

Keywords: *Senecio grandidentatus*, systematics, vegetative, anatomical, bioecological

Ключевые слова: *Senecio grandidentatus*, систематика, вегетативный, анатомический, биоэкологический

One of the priority issues of our time is the study and conservation of the biological diversity of plant cover. This matter is complex and multifaceted. Since the 20th century, numerous scientific studies have been carried out to solve this problem. The use of modern methods in the study of plant cover plays an essential role in addressing these issues.

The functioning of a plant organism is determined not only by the environmental factors affecting the plants but also by the specificity of the organism's

genetic characteristics, which are shaped by ecological and historical conditions. Therefore, it is vital to study the systematics of plant genera and species, their taxonomic composition, and clarify nomenclatural changes based on anatomical-morphological analyses. Taking this into account, we conducted a systematic, bioecological, and anatomical-morphological study of the species *Senecio grandidentatus* Lebed., a member of the Asteraceae family, found in the flora of Azerbaijan.

Materials and Methods:

The research was conducted in 2022-2023 in the flora of Azerbaijan. Herbarium specimens of *Senecio grandidentatus* Lebed. were collected from various ecological conditions, prepared according to standard methods, and the species' systematic position was determined using commonly accepted guidelines, including APG IV (www.Worldfloraonline.org), World Flora Online, and The Euro-Med Plantbase (<http://ww2.bgbm.org/>) [5, 6, 7]. The bioecological characteristics of the species were studied using "Flora of Azerbaijan" by A.M. Asgarov's "The Plant World of Azerbaijan" (Asgarov, 2016), "Conspectus Florae Caucasicae" Volume VIII (2012), works by N.N. Porteniyer (Porteniyer, 2012), and other scientists [1, 2, 3, 4].

The morphological characteristics of vegetative organs were studied using the MBS-2 binocular loupe, and the prepared slides were examined with Biolom and MBI-3 microscopes. The thickness of sections, leaf, petiole, root parts, and cell sizes were measured using an ocular micrometer. Anatomical images were captured using an RA-2 camera, an MI-4100 D microscope, and a Tucsen camera (Baranov, 1925; Baranova, 1985; Zakhariyevich, 1954; Rumyantseva, 2022) [8, 9, 10, 11].

Specimens for the study were collected from the Shamakhi region at an altitude of 1257 meters above sea level, from the *Elytrigetum–Astracanthosum*

formation group of the mountain xerophyte plant community, specifically from the *Elytrigia elongatiformis–Astracanthosum denudata* association.

The phytocoenosis consisted of 24 species: 2 shrub species (8.3%) *Astracantha denudata* (Stev.) Podlech., *Paliurus spina–Christii* Mill.), 2 subshrub species (8.3%) (*Astracantha caspica* (Bieb.) Podlech., *Rosa cuspidata* Bieb.), 11 perennial herbaceous species (45.8%) (*Elytrigia elongatiformis* (Drob.) Nevski., *Agropyrum puberulum* (Boiss.ex.Steud.Beauv., *Botrichloa ischaemum* (L.) Keng., *Agropyron cristatum* (L.) Gaerth., *Festuca rupicola* Heuff., *Stipa capillata* L., *Hordeum bulbosum* L., *Teucrium orientale* L., *Phlomis pungens* Willd., *Kaolera cristata* (L.) Pers., *Senecio grandidentatus* Lebed.), and 9 annual herbaceous species (37.5%) (*Medicago orbicularis* (L.) Bartalini., *Astragalus brachyceras* Lebed., *Chamaemelum inodorum* (L.) Vis., *Algilops cylindrica* Host, *Allium rubellum* L., *Bromus japonicus* Thunb., *Trifolium echinofum* Bieb., *Lolium rigidum* Gaudin., *Lappula squarrosa* Bankex Stand.).

Among these species, 15 (62.5%) are xerophytes, 6 (25%) are mesoxerophytes, and 3 (12.5%) are mesophytes. The dominant species of this formation is *Astracantha denudata* with an abundance rating of 3-4, while the subdominant is *Elytrigia elongatiformis* with a rating of 2-3. The abundance of *Senecio grandidentatus* Lebed. was rated as 1.

Şəkil 1. *Senecio grandidentatus* Lebed.

Senecio grandidentatus (Fl. Ross., II, 636 (1845—1846); A. Grosseym, Фл. Кавк., IV, 154 (1934)) is a perennial herbaceous plant species (Figure 1). The plant has erect stems that can reach a height of 0.3 to 2.0 meters. Its leaves are pinnately lobed with wide or narrow oblong segments and appear feather-like. The lower leaves on the stem have long petioles, while the middle and upper leaves are deeply lobed, sparsely feathered, sessile, and have auricles clasping the stem. The bisexual flowers are 1.5-2.5 cm in diameter, grouped in dense, flat-topped corymbs. The ray florets are golden yellow, and the disc florets are bright yellow, longer than the involucre. The species has a long flowering period from June to November.

Senecio grandidentatus is commonly found in the forests of the middle mountain belt. Its flowering and fruiting periods occur from June to September. In terms of its ecological characteristics, it is classified as a

mesophyte. In Azerbaijan, it is distributed in the Greater Caucasus, Lesser Caucasus, Lankaran, and Nakhchivan mountainous areas. Its overall distribution includes regions such as Asia Minor and Iran.

Taxonomy:

Order: Asterales

Family: Asteraceae Bercht. et J.Presl

Tribe: Senecioneae Cass.

Genus: *Senecio* L.

Species: *Senecio grandidentatus* Lebed.

The collected material was preserved in 700-proof alcohol. Both fresh and alcohol-preserved specimens were used to prepare temporary and permanent slides. The slides were prepared according to commonly accepted anatomical methods. Sections were stained with safranin and alcohol-based fluoroquinoline solution.

Leaf Anatomy. As is known, the leaf is the most plastic organ of a plant. The structure of the leaf reflects not only the ecological and climatic conditions in which a particular species develops but also the adaptation responses of the organism to the environmental conditions during specific growth periods. Therefore,

studying the anatomical and morphological structure of leaves allows for a deeper understanding of the ecological features of the plant and reveals its degree of adaptation to its habitat. Certain features in the leaf structure provide clues to which ecological group the plant belongs to.

Figure 2. Anatomical structure of the leaf

1-upper epidermis; 2-lower epidermis; 3-guticle; 4 - palisade parenchyma tissue; 5 - spongy parenchyma tissue; 6-central vascular bundle; 7 - glandular trichome

The epidermis is covered by a thick cuticle layer. Below the upper epidermis, the mesophyll tissue contains two layers of cylindrical palisade parenchyma cells. Inside the mesophyll tissue, spongy parenchyma cells are present. The leaves are dorsiventral, meaning they have distinct upper and lower surfaces. In the central vein, between the upper and lower epidermis, multiple layers of collenchyma cells are observed. The small vascular bundles are collateral in type. The leaves are amphistomatic, meaning stomata are found on both the upper and lower epidermis. The stomata are located at the same level as the epidermal cells. On the adaxial (upper, ventral) surface of the leaf, anomocytic type stomata are observed in the epidermal cells. The palisade parenchyma cells are oval and circular in shape. The spongy parenchyma cells have large intercellular spaces (Figure 2).

structure. Small glandular trichomes are observed scattered on the epidermis. Beneath the epidermis, 4-5 layers of chlorenchyma tissue cells are present. The chlorenchyma tissue alternates with layered collenchyma sections, giving the stem a slightly wavy appearance. Inside the chlorenchyma, large parenchyma cells are located, and the size of these cells decreases around the vascular bundles. Between the cortex parenchyma and the phloem, 5-7 layers of sclerenchyma sections are observed. Sclerenchyma cells have thick walls. Moving inward from the phloem, the cambium is found, which consists of 2-3 layers of thin-walled cells. The vascular bundles are open collateral in type. The xylem is oriented toward the center of the stem, while the phloem is directed toward the epidermis. The center of the stem consists of the pith, represented by parenchyma cells (Figure 3).

The stem of the mature generative plant is covered externally by a single-layer epidermis with a typical

Figure 3. Anatomical structure of the trunk

1 - Epidermis, 2 - Chlorenchyma, 3 - Cortex parenchyma, 4 - Glandular trichome, 5 - Sclerenchyma, 6 - Phloem, 7 - Xylem, 8 - Pith, 9 - Cambium

Root. In a cross-section, the root is circular in shape and surrounded by a single layer of periderm cells, which have become corky. Beneath the periderm, the primary cortex elements are located. The mesoderm is represented by 8-9 layers of parenchyma. The endoderm differs from the parenchyma tissue by

having smaller, densely packed cells. The pericycle is not clearly visible because it consists of thin-walled and very small cells. The central cylinder occupies about one-third of the cross-sectional area of the root, with significant development of xylem elements observed (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Anatomical structure of the root
1 – periderm, 2 – bark parenchyma, 3-phloem, 4 - xylem

The rhizome of the plant has a non-ball structure, it is covered with periderm from the outside. A shell consisting of parenchyma cells is located inward from the periderm, in its inner part - at the border with the

stele - oval-shaped secretory sites of schizogenous origin are observed. 2/3 of the root is occupied by the bark, and 1/4 is occupied by the core parenchyma. Xylem is strongly developed (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Root-like anatomical structure
1 – periderm, 2 – bark parenchyma, 3 – secretory site, 4 – phloem, 5 – cambium, 6 – xylem, 7 – core

As a result of the researches, during the anatomical analysis of the vegetative organs of the *Senesio grandidentatus* plant, the following characteristics were determined: leaves have a dorsoventral structure, the leaf is amphistomous and the leaflets are anomocytic type, the mesophyll is heterogeneous type, the transmitting balls are open-collateral type, the surface of the stem is covered with glandular hairs, layered collenchyma cells together with chlorenchyma gives a wavy appearance to the stem, strong development of xylem is observed in the root. Excretory places of schizogenic origin were formed in *Kökumsov*. As mentioned, the bioecological characteristics and some diagnostic signs of *S. grandidentatus* species have been revealed. The determined results will be used in the phylogenetic evaluation among the species of the genus *Senesio*.

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